

PROFILING DISTRIBUTED EXECUTION OF RDATAFRAME APPLICATIONS WITH JIT-ED CODE

August 2022

AUTHOR(S):

Giulio Crognaletti

CERN, EP-SFT

SUPERVISOR(S):

Vincenzo Eduardo Padulano

Enric Tejedor Saavedra

ABSTRACT

When running an analysis application distributedly, a crucial feature is the ability to monitor, debug and profile the execution of the application, a task that is rendered more complex in the presence of JIT-ed code. In the following report an overview of the power of Cling new JIT-ed profiling feature is given, underlining its strength and weaknesses. Afterwards, this important feature is exploited to devise and implement a profiling strategy for RDataFrame applications with JIT-ed code in the *distributed* case. Finally some tests are performed and the result compared to the local profiling.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

.....

1	INTRODUCTION	3
1.1	Profiling RDataFrame	3
2	PROFILING OF JIT-ED CODE (LOCAL SYSTEMS)	4
2.1	Requirements	4
2.2	Possible visualizations	5
2.3	Results and observations	6
2.3.1	Toy Examples - JIT-ed code	6
2.3.2	Toy Examples - External libraries	9
2.3.3	Realistic Example	10
3	PROFILING OF JIT-ED CODE (DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS)	10
3.1	Main ideas	11
3.2	Requirements and default settings	12
3.3	The user's perspective: how to use the feature	12
3.4	Results	13
3.4.1	Technical details	14
3.4.2	Flamegraphs	14
4	CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK	16
5	REFERENCES	17

1 INTRODUCTION

When running an analysis application distributedly, a crucial feature is the ability to monitor, debug and profile the execution of the application. While task monitoring and debugging messages are provided to a certain extent by distributed computing schedulers such as Dask [2] or Spark [7], there is a clear lack of proper profiling information of a distributed execution, particularly in code that mixes Python with C++. Moreover, the presence of JIT-ed code in the applications can add another level of complexity to the problem of collecting meaningful profiling data. This project focuses on the implementation of a profiling mechanism for applications based on ROOT's `RDataFrame` data analysis tool [1] [6], and in particular on the distributed version (DistRDF) [5]. Profiling data produced in this way is then analyzed by means of visualization tools, in particular FlameGraphs.

1.1 Profiling RDataFrame

Given some data-set organized into named columns, `RDataFrame` provide the users an interface composed of several actions and transformations to manipulate their data. Such transformations will take a C++ function and some `RDataFrame` columns as input and apply the function according the prescribed transformation over the whole data-set. To further clarify this notion, the following examples illustrates the typical usage of the C++ APIs in the case of the "Define" transformation:

```
float compute_energy(ROOT::RVecF p, float m){
    float p2 = p[0]*p[0]+p[1]*p[1]+p[2]*p[2]
    return std::sqrt(p2+m*m)
}
...
//treeName contains two columns, "momentum" and "mass"
auto d = ROOT::RDataFrame("treeName","file.root")
//This adds a new "energy" column to the data-set
auto d1 = d.Define("energy", compute_energy, {"momentum","mass"})
```

Even if `RDataFrame` is used through its Python interface, such manipulations are still performed by the underlying C++ code, and consequently user defined functions cannot be provided as Python functions¹ (that would be in analogy to the above case), but rather as strings containing valid C++ code, that are subsequently JIT-ed by `Cling`, ROOT's C++ interactive interpreter. Alternatively, user functions can be declared to the interpreter in advance and then called inside those strings:

```
ROOT.gInterpreter.Declare("""
float p2(ROOT::RVecF p){
    return p[0]*p[0]+p[1]*p[1]+p[2]*p[2]}
""")

d = ROOT.RDataFrame("treeName","file.root")
d1 = d.Define("energy","std::sqrt(p2(momentum) + mass*mass)")
```

¹It would be possible to use Python functions provided that they are JIT-able by Numba. In fact, this feature is already being developed within the ROOT team.

In this case both strategies have been used. It is worthwhile to notice that here, column names are used directly within the C++ code string in the Define. These strings containing C++ code are automatically wrapped by RDataFrame in actual C++ functions named `rdf::func#`, where `#` is substituted by an incrementing integer counter for each new function declared this way. The JIT-ed functions resulting from this will take those columns as inputs without the need of further specification.

Up until very recently, the presence of such JIT-ed code prevented proper profiling of RDataFrame applications. Now, thanks to the new Cling profiling feature, it is possible to collect debug information for JIT-ed functions and use it in conjunction with profiling tools such as linux `perf` to produce meaningful visualization (e.g FlameGraphs) at least for local executions.

With this in mind, the goal of implementing a profiler for DistRDF has been divided into two main steps:

- At first, Cling's JIT-ed code profiling feature is tested in the case of RDataFrame on a local system.
This step was particularly important because it allowed to find the precise requirements for the profiling feature to work, and establish the level of accuracy that can be obtained using such technique with RDataFrame.
- Secondly, a mechanism to replicate the local results on a distributed system is devised and implemented.
This step is much less trivial than the first, and requires the synchronization of data collection and processing in each of the distributed nodes. All complications are taken care of in the newly proposed `DistRDF.Profiling` module.

2 PROFILING OF JIT-ED CODE (LOCAL SYSTEMS)

As previously stated, profiling of JIT-ed code is crucial in RDataFrame. In this section, an overview of the software requirements is presented, together with some observations on the quality of the obtained results.

2.1 Requirements

Before starting to profile RDataFrame applications with JIT-ed code using profiling tools such as linux `perf`, it is important that some requirements are satisfied. In particular:

- **Build ROOT with debug options**

ROOT must be built from source with debug options. Moreover, the `"-fno-omit-frame-pointer"` compiler flag must also be set for the ROOT build. More precisely, the `cmake` options used during the build were:

```
$ cmake -DCMAKE_CXX_FLAGS_RELWITHDEBINFO="-O2 -g -fno-omit-frame-pointer"
-DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE="RelWithDebInfo" -DLLVM_BUILD_TYPE="RelWithDebInfo"
```

Even if its presence can add some overhead, the flag `"-fno-omit-frame-pointer"` is crucial to obtain meaningful call-stacks and cannot be omitted.

- **Make sure to have permission to collect PMU events of interest**

Possible ways to do so using `perf`:

- Restrict collection to events available in user-space
- Lower `perf`'s paranoid level (requires superuser privileges)

- **Set the environment variable `CLING_PROFILE = 1` before Cling gets initialized**

This step is crucial to signal the interactive interpreter to start collecting debug information for JIT-ed functions and dump it to disk in a `perf`-readable format.

In the python case, this step must be done before the `"import ROOT"` statement is run in the application. Locally, this step is trivial since the variable can be manually set in the environment before execution of the application to be profiled.

- **Install debug packages for the external libraries used (e.g. glibc)**

This final requirement is not strictly necessary, but is useful to complete the call stacks with information coming from external libraries. If not present, the detail of the specific calls within those libraries will be lost.

Once all the requirements are fulfilled, raw profiling data can be effectively collected using the `perf record` command.

2.2 Possible visualizations

Raw data produced by `perf record` can be analyzed in detail using the `perf report` tool. However, using data visualizations is key in profiling since they efficiently convey most of the information in more direct and readable way.

The tools used during the project are:

- **Flame Graph** [4] Flame graphs are very popular visualization tools that display call stacks as box stacks whose width is proportional to the time spent in the respective function (more precisely, the width of each box represents the *fraction of samples* collected for the respective function). A detailed description can be found in the original [github repository](#) and [website](#) by Brendan Gregg.
- **Graph representation** [3] Graph representations also displays function calls as boxes, but connects them in a (possibly cyclic) graph to convey the information of the call flow. This representation is more compact but can be harder to read. A detailed description can be found in the original [github repository](#) by Jose Fonseca.

Note: Neither of the two representation give information about the *order of execution in time* of functions, but rather condense equal call stacks into the same square, thus giving an idea of the overall time spent in each call stack.

In the subsequent sections, FlameGraphs will be preferred. For a more complete description of the tests performed, refer to my github repository [Profiling-RDF](#).

The same example is proposed also for the Python case, with the following result (green tiles represent JIT-ed functions):

Figure 2: Python JIT-ed toy example

Here, the functions analogous to `calc_x()`, `calc_y()` and `waste_time()` are not declared to the interpreter in advance (see Section 1.1), so they do not have a function name and appear instead as a unified function named `R_rdf::func#`. Still the overall structure is the same, which is to be expected.

If however, such intermediate functions are declared to the interpreter, the following graph will be obtained:

Figure 3: Python JIT-ed toy example - Explicit function declaration to Cling

In this new plot, the `calc_x()` and `calc_y()` functions disappeared, and the corresponding

call-stacks look merged. It seems like only functions with a meaningful workload appear in the plot, possibly due to *inlining*, and this can result in the merging of few different call-stacks.

Additionally, the signatures appearing in the templates of `RDF::RDefine` or analogous `RDataFrame` transformation, are not to be trusted to infer the typing of the user defined function.

In fact, `RDF::RDefine` is always templated based on the signature of the C++ wrapper produced by `Cling` (i.e. `R_rdf::func#`), even if it contains only one function call. Moreover, such signature always coincides with a subset of column types, and does not take into account the constant factors or type conversions done in the user defined function.

To be clearer, let's consider the following example:

Assume the analysis is parameterized using functions similar to the following, declaring them to the interpreter in advance

```
int calc_x_with_options(int x, float param, bool opt, double another_param);
int calc_y_with_options(int y, bool opt, bool another_opt, unsigned long long param);
```

and then using them like this

```
dx = d.Define("x", "calc_x_with_options((int)rdfentry_, 1.5, true, -2.65e8)")
dy = dx.Define("y", "calc_y_with_options((int)rdfentry_, true, false, 100201302)")
```

then, the resulting graph will look like this:

Figure 4: Python JIT-ed toy example - Signatures are not faithful

It is very clear in this graph that in this case, `RDF::RDefine` is templated based on a different signature, that takes into account the type of `_rdfentry_`, i.e. `unsigned long long`, but not the signature of the user defined function, that included many other options, nor the cast to `int` performed.

2.3.2 Toy Examples - External libraries

Some extra care must also be taken when analyzing code that uses external libraries. In particular, if the user is interested in the detail of the specific calls within those libraries, the debug packages must be installed. But even in this case, call-stacks can break.

Lets consider the following example: a fully compiled C++ RDataFrame is created with one column *x* computed using the following function

```
double calc_x(ULong64_t entry)
{
    double s = 1.0;
    for (int i = 0; i < LOOP_REPS; ++i){s = std::sin(s);}
    return s;
}
```

calc_x calls into the C++ STL, that provides the mathematical functions. The resulting graph is the following:

Figure 5: Fully compiled C++ toy example - External library calls

The symbol referring to the `std::sin()` call should be on top of `calc_x()`, but instead appear on the side. This phenomenon is due to the fact that, even though the library provides debug information, it is still not compiled with `"-fno-omit-frame-pointer"`, that is necessary to have precise stacks. In fact, if the same example is run on a machine where `glibc` is compiled with the correct flag the problem disappears

Figure 6: Fully compiled C++ toy example - External library calls (solved)

Note: This phenomenon is probably of interest only in very refined analyses. In more coarse performance studies rough estimates of the correct call-stack can be inferred using knowledge about the profiled code (e.g. which functions call the external library), so that in typical case studies, using libraries other than ROOT compiled with "-fno-omit-frame-pointer" is by no means necessary to obtain meaningful visualizations.

2.3.3 Realistic Example

With all the previous observations in mind, it is now possible to take a look to a more realistic example, i.e. the W Boson analysis [RDataFrame tutorial](#). This tutorial contains the analysis of the W boson mass taken from a small subset of the ATLAS Open Data released in 2020. Since in this case the workload was very small due to the limited dimension of the data-set, each user defined function has been rendered more expensive with busy loops, obtaining the following results:

Figure 7: Python JIT-ed realistic example - W Boson analysis

In this final plot it is possible to distinguish all the user defined functions, both declared to Cling in advance and not, which allows profiling of JIT-ed code from the users!

3 PROFILING OF JIT-ED CODE (DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS)

To parallelize the execution of RDataFrame applications, the ROOT package provides an experimental feature that leverages schedulers such as Dask or Spark to scatter the workload on distributed systems and gather the results in the client. Some of these tools (i.e. Dask), already provides some profiling tools and visualizations, however they are not as detailed as the results shown above. Moreover, such tools use python profilers that cannot capture the underlying

C++ calls made by RDataFrame. The mechanism described below instead, allows to collect profiling data using perf, and produce the above visualizations on a distributed architecture.

In the following, the profiling feature inner workings are described and the new profiling API presented. Finally some results are shown for a specific example.

3.1 Main ideas

In order to devise a profiling mechanism for distributed RDataFrame applications, is necessary to understand how the workload is split between the distributed workers and the results are gathered and merged. In our case, a map-reduce scheme is used, that can be briefly summarized as follows:

- **Map phase:** Data is split into partitions, each of which is processed by a worker using a **mapper** function. Here the calculations are performed in parallel between the workers, and results are stored locally in temporary storage in each distributed node.
- **Reduce phase:** The results are gathered from different distributed nodes and merged recursively using a **reducer** function, to produce the final result to be sent to the client.

The main idea in profiling DistRDF is to exploit the same map-reduce dynamics also for the collection of profiling data and production of the visualizations. In this way, it is possible to build on the already existing implementation of the same scheme by decorating **mapper** and **reducer** functions with the task of collecting and merging profiling data.

The following picture show the general workflow of such profiling mechanism:

Figure 8: General profiling mechanism for DistRDF

At first, the client side communicate to all distributed workers that the profiling feature must be activated. This is achieved by sending to each worker a decorated **mapper** function, that collects profiling data and performs some pre-processing. Once this phase is finished, the mechanism used to merge results is exploited to also merge pre-processed data, that is collected in the client. Finally, the client can produce the full visualization, e.g. a FlameGraph of the distributed execution.

Of course, the user doesn't need to coordinate all of this to use the feature, but rather this mechanism is used in the `DistrRDF.Profiling` module, implemented as part of the project.

Up to now, only a specific implementation to produce FlameGraphs from `perf` data has been carried out and included in the newly introduced module. However, the strategy is very general and not limited to that, and in fact the code is very modular and easily extendable to support different visualizations and/or profilers. For more details, refer to the project github repository.

3.2 Requirements and default settings

In the following we restrict the attention to the already implemented case of producing FlameGraphs using `perf` data. In order for the feature work correctly in the distributed case, some simple requirements need to be satisfied in *each* node. In particular:

- All node must comply to the requirements specified in Section 2.1
- Data pre-processing utilities (i.e. `stackcollapse-perf.pl` from Brendan Gregg's repository) must present in the nodes and their location added to the "PATH" environment variable. This constraint comes from the fact that such utilities must be programmatically run by the profiler in each node.
- The user running the profiler must have permission to collect PMU of interest in each node. This constraint comes from the restrictions put in place by `perf` itself, and cannot be circumvented.

As stated in Section 2.1, there are multiple ways of dealing with data collection permission issues, and users may choose the most suitable one based on their analyses needs and/or control over the machines used. By default, `DistrRDF.Profiling` automatically restricts collection of data to user space². More specifically, the default configuration is:

- **Metric:** CPU cycles in user-space (option "`-e cycles:u`").
- **Buffer Size:** Data collection buffer size is limited to 16KB. This setting is key when working in user-space, since in that case buffer memory is limited (option "`-m 16K`").
- **Data Maximum size:** Output data size is limited to 50MB to avoid excessive disk usage by the profiler (option "`--max-size 50M`").
- **Sampling Frequency:** 99Hz (option "`-F 99`").

The defaults provide a good working solution to many of the subtleties present when dealing with `perf`. However *any* of the above options can be easily changed by users through the new `DistrRDF.Profiling` python interface to match their needs.

3.3 The user's perspective: how to use the feature

From the user's perspective, the profiling feature described above is accessible in ROOT as a context manager called `ClingProfile` that can be imported from the RDF Experimental package as `ROOT.RDF.Experimental.Distributed.ClingProfile`.

²This comes with some limitations, for instance a limited data collection buffer size, to be shared among all processes running `perf` on the same node.

The usage is very simple, and can be divided into steps:

- **Create the a RDataFrame and distributed client instance:** Users are free to create an instance of Distributed RDataFrame using any of the supported client types before activating the feature.
- **Enter the ClingProfile context manager:** To do so, the user must use a `with` statement, providing the newly created RDataFrame instance as a parameter to `ClingProfile` constructor as the first argument. Additional keyword arguments can be added to specify profiler and/or visualization options (e.g. `perf` options).
- **Code the analysis:** From within the `with` statement, the user can code the rest of the application, caring to include the event loop trigger inside (e.g. `GetValue` calls, etc.).

In the following, a specific example of such use case is provided:

```
# Import the necessary modules from ROOT
import ROOT
RDataFrame = ROOT.RDF.Experimental.Distributed.Dask.RDataFrame
ClingProfile = ROOT.RDF.Experimental.Distributed.ClingProfile

# Create the distributed client
client = create_dask_client(...)

# Create RDF instance
df = RDataFrame("Events", files, npartitions=npartitions, daskclient=client)

# The profiling feature will be active for all event loops triggered
# within the ClingProfile context
with ClingProfile(df, perf_options = {"--max-size":"10M", "-F":"20"}):

    df = df.Filter(...)
    ...
    df.GetValue() # <- Event Loop trigger is inside
```

As shown here, profiler options can be passed to constructor as dictionary, where keys represent the options to change and values the corresponding new values. In this case, the user decided to explicitly limit the disk usage to 20MB and lower the sampling frequency to 20 Hz. By doing so, the profiling will be active for all event loops triggered within the `ClingProfile` context, with the new `perf` options in place of the defaults.

Note: The feature will be active only for the RDataFrame instance specified to the constructor of `ClingProfile`, and not all RDataFrame instances.

3.4 Results

In order to assess the profiling feature, some tests have been performed. In particular, the analysis of the di-muon spectrum using data from the CMS detector has been used as a benchmark

to check the feature on a distributed machine. Code for the analysis is very simple, and can be found in the official CMS open data repository on github.

3.4.1 Technical details

On a more technical level, for all tests, a Dask SSH Cluster based Distributed RDataFrame instance has been used to run the application on a 3-node cluster with 2 computing nodes, each of which had 4 physical cores, and 1 scheduler node. Data was split into 8 partitions, for each of which a worker process has been spawned (one per physical core). Since the data-set was not too large, a copy of it was saved in each machine’s local drive, to make data cheaply accessible, and all of the options were fixed to the defaults.

3.4.2 Flamegraphs

The application was run with profiling feature activated, obtaining the following results:

Figure 9: Di-muon analysis on a distributed system

In this case we still can clearly distinguish the contribution of each step of the analysis as in the local case, from the decompression of data (e.g. `inflate_fast` from `libz`) to the JIT-ed functions in green.

Since the architecture use to test is very simple, it was possible to manually exploit profiling data temporarily saved to disk in the nodes to produce FlameGraphs of the local execution of their fraction of the workload. As a comparison, also those local graphs are shown:

Figure 10: Flamegraphs obtained from profiling data in node 1.

Figure 11: Flamegraphs obtained from profiling data in node 2.

As we can see, all three graphs look very similar, and indeed the complete graph obtained by the merged profiling data is nothing but the average among all the single nodes' graphs.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

To conclude, the work here presented lead to two main results:

- **The precise requirements to build accurate call stacks using Cling's profiling feature have been identified**, and the degree of accuracy achieved by Cling JIT-ed code profiling feature assessed. In particular, in order for it to work is crucial that ROOT is built using the "-fno-omit-frame-pointer" flag
- **A mechanism to produce the same analysis for the distributed case have been devised and implemented** in the `DistRDF.Profiling` module. This feature provides a clean API that allows the user to collect profiling data and produce visualizations in the distributed case, making little to no changes to the code.

In the future, support to new profilers (e.g. python profilers) and visualization (e.g. graph-based visualizations) can be added. Moreover, given the similarity between the results of different nodes, a possible solution to save computational resources could be to profile only *few* nodes instead of all, getting a fairly good estimate of the merged graph using far less data.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] I. Antcheva et al. “ROOT — A C++ framework for petabyte data storage, statistical analysis and visualization”. In: *Computer Physics Communications* 180.12 (2009). 40 YEARS OF CPC: A celebratory issue focused on quality software for high performance, grid and novel computing architectures, pp. 2499–2512. ISSN: 0010-4655. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2009.08.005>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0010465509002550>.
- [2] Dask Development Team. *Dask: Library for dynamic task scheduling*. 2016. URL: <https://dask.org>.
- [3] José Fonseca. *gprof2dot*. URL: <https://github.com/jrfonseca/gprof2dot>.
- [4] Brendan Gregg. “The Flame Graph: This Visualization of Software Execution is a New Necessity for Performance Profiling and Debugging.” In: *Queue* 14.2 (Mar. 2016), pp. 91–110. ISSN: 1542-7730. DOI: [10.1145/2927299.2927301](https://doi.org/10.1145/2927299.2927301). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2927299.2927301>.
- [5] Vincenzo Eduardo Padulano et al. “Distributed data analysis with ROOT RDataFrame”. In: *EPJ Web Conf.* 245 (2020), p. 03009. DOI: [10.1051/epjconf/202024503009](https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202024503009).
- [6] Danilo Piparo et al. “RDataFrame: Easy Parallel ROOT Analysis at 100 Threads”. In: *EPJ Web Conf.* 214 (2019), p. 06029. DOI: [10.1051/epjconf/201921406029](https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/201921406029).
- [7] Matei Zaharia et al. “Apache spark: A unified engine for big data processing”. In: *Communications of the ACM* 59 (Nov. 2016), pp. 56–65. DOI: [10.1145/2934664](https://doi.org/10.1145/2934664).

